

Conference Abstract

Parameterizing water column dynamics of Lake Lunz using the MyLake model

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Abstract

Lake Lunz is located in the North-Eastern Calcareous Alps in Austria at an Elevation of 600 m. The lake underwent massive changes in terms of stratification pattern, surface water temperature and ice cover from about 1980 onwards. In the recent years, Lake Lunz exhibited increasing levels of oxygen depletion in deeper strata from late summer onwards.

In order to study the causality underlying the changes in oxygen depletion and in an attempt to make sound projections into future climate scenarios we parameterized the water column dynamics employing the MyLake model, making use of available observational data both from Lake Lunz as well as meteorological data. The MyLake model overall reproduces water column dynamics very well and responds sensitively to year to year climatic conditions. We use two RCP scenarios to simulate the water column dynamics under future climatic conditions.

Keywords

Limnology, Lakes, Global Change, Modeling, MyLake, LakeEnsemblR, Lake Lunz

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Conflicts of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.